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Research Article

INCIDENCE OF MOTORBIKE ACCIDENTS AND PATTERN OF INJURIES PRESENTING IN EMERGENCY IN LAHORE, PAKISTAN

Muhammad Abdullah hashmi¹, Khalid Mehmood Arif², Muhammad Daud Ibrahim³, Saad Javaid⁴, Ammad Javaid Chaudhary⁵

House Officer, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad, Email: hashmirulz807@gmail.com,² House Officer, Mayo Hospital. Lahore, Email: Romiohell@yahoo.com,³ Medical Officer, RHC, Chiniot, Email: muhammaddaudibrahim342@gmail.com,⁴ MBBS, MD, Medical Officer, Ashraf Naseer Medical center, Multan, Email: saadjavaid289abc@gmail.com;⁵ MBBS, MD, Medical Officer, Ashraf Naseer Medical center, Multan, Email: Ammadjavaidchaudhary@gmail.com;

Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of our study was to find Incidence of Motorbike and Associated Pattern of Injuries. **Duration of Study:** This study was carried out in a period of 9 months from February 2018 to October 2018. **Place of Study:** This study was carried out in accidents and emergency department of Mayo Hospital Lahore. **Materials and Methods:** Patients between the ages of 6- 70 years were included in this study regardless of their gender and patients had all kind of injuries. All the patients who presented in emergency department with road traffic accidents were selected and following inclusion criteria patients were selected. Injuries were classified according to different regions involved. Complete examination was done on each patient and related investigations were done to find the associated injuries. A pre designed proforma was used to collect the data of the patients. Informed consent was taken from all the patients and ethical committee approval was taken. **Results:** A total of 2000 patients were studied in a duration of 9 months. Patients were between the ages of 6-70 years with the mean age of 31.4 years. Among these 1588(79.4%) belonged to male gender while 412(20.6%) were females. 1136(58.8%) patients suffered from injuries to lower limbs while upper limb injuries were seen in 544(27.2%) of the patients. Other results are as follows;

1. Abrasions	1874 (93.7%)
2. Bruises	1040 (52%)
3. Lacerations	1362 (68.1%)
4. Fractures in lower limbs	450 (22.5%)
5 Fractures in upper limbs	272 (13.6%)

Keywords: Motorbike accidents, fractures, Abrasions, Injury pattern.

Corresponding author:

Muhammad Abdullah hashmi,
House Officer, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad,
Email: hashmirulz807@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

In the urban cities of underdeveloped countries, motorbike is a major mode of transportation. Bike fanatics, low socioeconomic status, type of job forces the individuals to use this mode of transportation.[1] Deficiency of respect for traffic guidelines, escalation of traffic load, enhanced road conditions, rash driving and stunts by bike fanatics and teenagers have increased the incidence of road traffic accidents by a large number. [2] Pattern of injuries associated with bike accidents have been changed because of rash driving and growing passion for stunts while driving by bike fanatics. [3,4,5] It is a nagging problem of national concern and has a great impact on economic conditions, health and life of individuals and communities. [6]

It is a problem that is neglected in the entire world especially developing nations. Characteristic of injury varies from compound fractures to abrasions and other fatal injuries that threatens the life of individual. Apart from increased financial load on the family and government, death rate also increases with the increasing severity of injury. [7,8] In causing disabilities and death all over the globe, it is one of the leading cause. [9,10]

This study was carried out to reveal the types of injuries suffered in motorbike accidents. This study will help in development of proper trauma units where man power will be used to manage the patient on urgent basis in emergency department.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Patients between the ages of 6-70 years were included in this study regardless of their gender and patients had all kind of injuries. All the patients who presented in emergency department with road traffic accidents were selected and following inclusion criteria patients were selected. Injuries were classified according to different regions involved. Complete examination was done on each patient and related investigations were done to find the associated injuries. A pre designed

proforma was used to collect the data of the patients. Informed consent was taken from all the patients and ethical committee approval was taken.

RESULTS:

A total of 2000 patients were studied in a duration of 9 months. Patients were between the ages of 6-70 years with the mean age of 31.4 years. Among these 1588(79.4%) belonged to male gender while 412(20.6%) were females. 1136(58.8%) patients suffered from injuries to

lower limbs while upper limb injuries were seen in 544(27.2%) of the patients. Other results are as follows;

1. Abrasions (93.7%)	1874
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3. Lacerations (68.1%)	1362
4. Fractures in lower limbs	450 (22.5%)
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Fractures in spine was 28 (1.4%), skull and maxillofacial area 30 (1.5%), ribs 42 (2.1%) and pelvis 82 (4.1%).

DISCUSSIONS:

Accidents are a serious health issue and mostly teenagers are affected. [11] Deficiency of respect for traffic guidelines, escalation of traffic load, enhanced road conditions, rash driving and stunts by bike fanatics and teenagers have increased the incidence of road traffic accidents by a large number. [12,13,14] In old age, less number of injuries are seen but when they do occur they are serious in nature. [15,16,17] The results of our study are comparable to the studies done recently and in the past. It was shown by Khani GM [18] and coworkers that accidents mostly occur in young people. Motorbike accidents are commonly seen in young adults as shown by Khan A.²⁰ Young children are mostly affected as found by Fouda EY.¹³ Enhancing number of motorbike injuries in adolescents are children have been shown by Bevan CA [4].

In Pakistan high incidence is seen in males are they are the ones who drive motorbikes. [19,20] Accidents are more common in male gender as shown by Miki N [26] and similar results were shown by Sharma BR [32]. All these results are in accordance with our study showing males are more commonly involved in road traffic accidents. In females, injuries are mostly seen as a result of dupatta (long scarf) getting stuck in rear wheel causing the bike to slip. [21-23,23] Injuries around the neck are most common due to dupatta around the neck which is pulled when stuck in bike. [34,35,36] In female pillion riders motor bike accidents are more common as shown by Minhas MS [27].

Less number of injuries are seen in females because they are not active riders in Pakistan. Less injuries in females as compared to males is shown by Singh R and co-workers [34]. Lower limbs and pelvis fractures are most common because they are the first parts which touch the ground and are subjected to high amount of force. Enhanced fractures of lower limbs have

been shown by Kaimkhani GM, [18] Hofling [15], and Khan A [20].

The reactionary force provided by the hands to stop further injuries results in injuries to hands and upper limbs resulting in large number of injuries that fall 2nd to lower limb injuries. [25-29] Abrasions, bruises and lacerations occurs because of decreased force suffered due to secondary impact on the ground. Third most common injuries are seen in head and neck areas because helmets are not used by the bikers. [30-31] Injuries to the soft tissues and other viscera are less in number as shown by the study. Strict traffic regulations play a pivotal role in prevention of these injuries.

CONCLUSION:

Incidence of motorbike injuries is much higher in younger males who are bike fanatics. Among all the injuries seen abrasion and fractures of the lower limbs were most common.

REFERENCES:

1. Abedi L, Zavareh DK, Bazargani HS. Epidemiological pattern of motorcycle injuries with focus on riding purpose: Experience from a middle-income country. *J Anal Res Clin Med* 2015; 3(3): 149-156.
2. Aslam M, Taj TM, Ali SA, Mirza WA, Badar N. Non-fatal limb injuries in motorbike accidents. *J Coll of Phys Surg Pak* 2008; 18 (10): 635-638.
3. Banskota B, Shrestha S, Chaudhary RK, Rajbhandari T, Rijal S, Shrestha BK, et al. Patterns of Orthopaedic Injuries among Motorbike Accident Admissions Presenting to a Tertiary Care Hospital in Kathmandu. *J Nepal Health Res Counc* 2016;14(32):51-7
4. Bevan CA, Babl FE, Bolt P, Sharwood LN. The increasing problem of motorcycle injuries in children and adolescents. *Med J Aust* 2008; 189(1): 17-20
5. Cavalcanti AL, Ferriera FHC, Olinda RA, Padilha WWN, Cavalcanti AFC. Motorcycle related Cranio Maxillofacial injuries among Brazilian children and adolescents. *Biomed Pharmacol J* 2017; 10(4): 1603-09
6. Chalya PL, Mabula JB, Ngayomela IH, Kanumba ES, Chandika AB, Giiti G, et al. Motorcycle injuries as an emerging public health problem in Mwanza city, North Western Tanzania. *Tanzania J of health research* 2010; 12(4): 214-221
7. Cheon JY, Rice M. Off road motorbike and all-terrain vehicle/quadbike accidents in rural New South Wales. *J Trauma Treat* 2015; 4: 275-277
8. Craft G, Bui TV, Sidik M, Moore D, Sleet DA. A Comprehensive Approach to Motorcycle-Related Head Injury Prevention: Experiences from the Field in Vietnam, Cambodia, and Uganda. *Int J Environ Res Publ Health* 2017; 14(12): 1486
9. Debieux P, Chertman C, Mansur NSB, Dobashi E, Fernandes HJA. Musculoskeletal injuries in motorcycle accidents. *Acta Orthop Bras* 2010; 18 (6): 110-114.
10. Emiogun FE, Faduyile FA, Soyemi SS, Oyewole OO. Motorcycle accident mortality in Lagos, Nigeria: impact of a traffic law. *Afr J Trauma* 2016; 5: 43-47.
11. Faduyile FA, Emiogun F, Soyemi S, Oyewole O, Okeke U, Williams O. Pattern of injuries in fatal motorcycle accident seen in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital: An autopsy based study. *Open Access J Med Sci* 2017; 5(2): 112-116.
12. Fitzharris M, Dandona R, Kumar GA, Dandona L. Crash characteristics and patterns of injury among hospitalized motorized two-wheeled vehicle users in urban India. *BMC Pub health* 2009; 9: 11
13. Fouda EY, Youssef M, Emile SH, Elfeki H, Thabet W, Abdallah E, et al. Pattern of major injuries after motorcycle accidents in Egypt: The Mansoura Emergency Hospital experience. *Trauma* 2017; 19(1): 39-45
14. Ghaffari-fam S, Sarbazi E, Daemi A, Sarbazi MR, Nikbakht HA, Salarilak S. The Epidemiological Characteristics of Motorcyclists Associated Injuries in Road Traffics Accidents; A Hospital-Based Study. *Bull Emerg Trauma* 2016; 4(4): 223-229
15. Hofling I, Keinanen P, Kroger H. Injuries caused by motorcycle accidents – a 5 years survey of patients treated in Kuopio University Hospital. *Suomen ortopedia ja Traumatologia*. 2006; 3(29): 243-247
16. Hsieh CH, Liu HT, Hsu SY, Hsieh HY, Chen YC. Motorcycle related hospitalization of the elderly. *Biomed J* 2017; 40(2): 121-128
17. Johnson OE. Prevalence and pattern of road traffic accidents among commercial motorcyclists in a city in southern Nigeria. *Educ Res* 2012; 6(3): 537-542
18. KaimKhani GM, Humail SM, Anjum MP, Afridi HD. Pattern and severity of bony injuries among motorcyclist admitted in orthopedic ward. *J Dow Uni Health Sci* 2013; 7(2): 73-75
19. Kumar R, Muzamil M, Mahmood K, Bhatti A, Minhas S, Kumar V. Frequency of motorbike injuries, Helmet vs non Helmet wearing in

- Karachi, Pakistan. *Trauma Int* 2016; 2(1): 34-36
20. Khan A. Prevalence of Orthopedic injuries in motorcycle accidents in patients presented to Khalifa Gul Nawaz Teaching Hospital, Bannu. *Khyber J Med Sci* 2016; 9(2): 155-160
 21. K-Y Tham, E Seow, G Lau. Pattern of injuries in helmeted motorcyclists in Singapore. *Emerg Med J* 2004; 21: 478-482
 22. Lin MR, Kraus JF. A review of risk factors and patterns of motorcycle injuries. *Accident Anal Prev* 2009; 41(4):710-22.
 23. Lusk AC, Asgarzadeh M, Farvid MS. Database improvement for motor vehicle/bicycle crash analysis. *Inj Prev* 2015; 21: 221-230.
 24. Martin RHJ, Fredy CT, Cidronio AH, Cesar CRJ. Motorcyclists' Mortality Pattern in Colombia from 2000 to 2013: A Longitudinal Study. *Arch Med* 2017; 9(4): 7-10
 25. Mefire AC, Atashili J, Tsiagadigui JG, Fon-Awah C, Ngowe-Ngowe M. A prospective pilot cohort analysis of crash characteristics and pattern of injuries in riders and pillion passengers involved in motorcycle crashes in an urban area in Cameroon: lessons for prevention. *BMC Pub health* 2015; 15: 915-918
 26. Miki N, Martimbianco ALC, Hira LT, Fernandes HA, dos Reis FB. Profile of trauma victims of motorcycle accidents treated at hospital São Paulo. *Acta Orthop Bras* 2014; 22(4): 160-163
 27. Minhas SM, Sangani MM, Mahmood K, Bhatti A, Mughar A, Kumar R. Dupatta (long scarf) related injuries in female pillion riders in Karachi, Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2016; 66(11): 1458-61
 28. Odiwuor CW, Nyamusi E, Odero W. Incidence of Road Traffic Crashes and Pattern of Injuries among Commercial Motorcyclists in Naivasha Town. *Int J App Res* 2015; 1(11): 541-549
 29. Prasannan K, Sheeju PA. A descriptive study of pattern of injuries in driver and pillion rider victims of fatal two wheeler accidents. *Asian J Biomed and Pharm Sci* 2105; 5(45): 29-32.
 30. Sann S, Haworth N, King J, King N. Road crashes and long term disabilities: Implications for policy and its implementation in Cambodia. Proceedings of 2103 Australian road safety research policing and education conference. 28-30 August, Brisbane, Queensland.
 31. Sapkota D, Bista B, Adhikari SR. Economic costs associated with motorbike accidents in Kathmandu, Nepal.
 - a. *Front Pub Health* 2016; 4: 273-275
 32. Sharma BR, Gupta N, Sharma AK, Sharma S. Pattern of fatal motorized two-wheeler crash injuries in Northern India: Is safety helmet adequate prevention. *Trends Med Res* 2007; 2(1): 27-36
 33. Shehzad Y, Arshad A, Akhter N. Pattern of head injury and recovery in first and second rider in motor bike accidents. *J R Med Coll* 2017; 21(1); 33-36
 34. Singh R, Singh HK, Gupta SC, Kumar Y. Pattern, severity and circumstances of injuries sustained in road traffic accident: a tertiary care hospital based study. *Indian J Community Med* 2014; 39(1): 30-34.
 35. Yousaf MN, Iqbal MJ, Akram MR, Chaudry RA. Pattern of Orthopedic injuries in motorcycle accidents. *Ann Pak Med Coll* 2013; 7(1): 77-84